

BRIGHAM YOUNG UNIVERSITY

CEEN 575

OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUES

Optimization of an IsoBeam for an Aircraft Floor Structure

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1 Abstract

This work performs an optimization of an IsoBeam structure. The IsoBeam is subjected to loads prescribed by FAA for floor beams of mid-size aircraft. Constraints for tension, buckling, deflection, and geometric bounds are imposed. The analysis is performed by a standard space frame analysis program written in Matlab. The optimizer made the middle of the longitudinal members the largest in order to satisfy the deflection constraint. The diagonal members at the ends were made the smallest because the deflection constraint was dominated by the stress and buckling constraint far from the middle. An optimized IsoBeam is 10% lighter than a similar aluminum beam.

2 Introduction

2.1 IsoTruss and IsoBeam Structures, CEEEn 602

In CEEEn 602, Composite Structures, we learned about the concept of IsoTruss structures. IsoTruss technology was developed at BYU by Dr. Jensen of the Civil Engineering Department and others, more than fifteen years ago. It has been described as the “ultimate composite structure” [1]. The premise of an IsoTruss is to use bundles of composite fiber material as small axial members of a space truss. Truss members only carry forces in the direction of the member. Composite fiber materials are the strongest in the direction of the fiber, making the use of composite fiber bundles in a space truss logical, and fully exploiting the strength of composite materials [2]. Because of this efficient use of lightweight composite material, IsoTruss structures have excellent strength to weight ratios [3].

An IsoTruss has a “Star of David” cross section, as seen in Figure 1. IsoTruss structures are best suited for applications of combined loading such as torsion, compression, and bending about multiple axes [4]. An IsoBeam is a geometric derivative of an IsoTruss [5] and has a rectangular cross section. IsoBeams are best suited for applications where they will only carry bending loads about a principal axes, such as with a floor beam. See Figure 2. In addition to weight savings, a unique benefit of using an IsoBeam as a floor joist is that there is no need to cut holes in the web because an IsoBeam naturally has many openings through which wires and piping can run.

2.2 Aircraft Floor Structure Project, CEEEn 523

In CEEEn 523, Aircraft Structures, there is a semester-long design project. The purpose of this project is to design the lowest weight floor beam that can carry the required loads and satisfy the required constraints. Boeing was the sponsor for this project, and provided the loadings and constraints [6]. There were 8 load cases involving different scenarios an aircraft might experience, such as depressurization of the cabin and an accelerated take-off. They also provided a deflection constraint; the beam must not deflect more than 1.5 inches under ultimate loads. This deflection constraint was mostly for the comfort of passengers.

Figure 1: Cross sections of the IsoTruss and the IsoBeam.

Figure 2: The IsoTruss and the IsoBeam

2.3 Space Frame Analysis Code, CEEEn 504

In CEEEn 504, Computer Structural Analysis, we derived and developed a matrix stiffness analysis code for space frames. It reads an input file that contains the coordinates of each joint, how the joints are connected, material properties, cross-sectional properties, support conditions, point loads, distributed loads, and support displacements. It is general enough to analyze frames or trusses. It then calculates displacement and local reactions for each member.

2.4 IsoBeam Floor Structure Optimization, CEEEn 575

When we were faced with the decision of what optimization problem to do, we decided to combine experiences from our previous classes. We thought it would be an interesting project and that the scope would be suitable for our Optimization class. The objective of our project was to minimize the weight of an IsoBeam suitable for application as an aircraft floor beam, subject to the roughly the same loadings and constraints we had in the aircraft floor structure project. We use the space frame analysis code we had already developed, and use the optimization techniques we learned in this class, CEEEn 575. The strong, but lightweight nature of an IsoBeam makes it an excellent prospect for an aircraft floor beam.

3 Methodology

We use the `fmincon` function from the Optimization Toolbox in MATLAB to minimize the IsoBeam weight. We chose `fmincon` because it is the most robust constrained optimization algorithm we are aware of and have experience with. We also suspected that our objective function, volume, was a continuous differentiable function.

3.1 Parameters

Most of our parameters came from either the CEEEn 523 project or from [5]. The length of our IsoBeam is 250 inches (20 ft) as per the Boeing instructions in the aircraft project [6]. We gathered the material properties, Young's modulus and the ultimate tensile strength from [5], based on the materials that IsoBeam structures have been made of before. Figures 3 and 4 show the dimensional quantities that define our IsoBeam, including L , h , w , and b . We decided to fix b at 10 inches. This results in 25 bays in a 250 inch long IsoBeam.

Another parameter that had to be passed into our optimization was the end fixities of all of the members. We modeled each connection of IsoBeam members as fixed-fixed. We did this because we believe that the nodes might be able to carry a moment. However, whether we modeled them as fixed-fixed or free-free generally had little effect. The geometry of an IsoBeam dictates that it's members will carry mostly axial loads regardless of the end fixities. Additionally we had to input values for the moment of inertia of each member. We input a value close to zero, $1e-6$, because we didn't want the members themselves to carry very much moment or shear.

Figure 3: Dimensional parameters for the IsoBeam

Figure 4: Isometric view of a single bay of an IsoBeam with different area groupings

3.2 Design Variables

It was not easy for us to choose our design variables and how many to have. It was clear to us that we couldn't make every member area and joint coordinate a design variable, but we wanted enough flexibility to have a near-optimal design. We also recognized the need for our design to be manufacturable. The first major decision we made was to keep the IsoBeam prismatic. That is, to have constant cross-sectional dimensions. We decided that the only dimensional design variables we would use would be the IsoBeam height and width.

It was an ever more difficult decision to try and figure out how many member area design variables to have. To have just one would result in an extremely overbuilt beam. To have one thousand, the number of elements in our IsoBeam, would be unmanufacturable. First, we decided a good way to split up the areas was into three groups; longitudinals, outer diagonals, and inner diagonals [5]. See Figure 4. In addition we decided to split up the beam into five different sections of five bays each. Each of these sections have those three design variables: areas of longitudinals, outer-diagonals, and inner-diagonals. Because the beam is symmetric, there are nine-additional variables, resulting in eleven total design variables.

3.3 Bound Constraints

We can formulate many of the necessary constraints we need as bound constraints. We include the following constraints:

1. Each area design variable has to be greater than $1e-6$. We tried setting this constraint greater than zero, but the stress explodes if that happens.
2. The height of the IsoBeam must be greater than 0 and less than 10.5 inches. This upper bound on the height is a constraint included by Boeing in their aircraft floor structure project [6]. This is to ensure that there is sufficient room in the cargo bays underneath. We expected that the optimizer would go towards 10.5 inches because that is the most efficient way to increase the effective moment of inertia of the IsoBeam, and thus be able to efficiently satisfy the deflection constraint.
3. The width of the IsoBeam must be greater than 5 inches and less than 24 inches. We included the minimum value of five inches to make sure the IsoBeam had a stout enough cross section to avoid lateral-torsional buckling (LTB). We included an upper-bound on the width because these floor beams will be placed every 24 inches, as per Boeing [6]. We expect that the optimizer will go towards the lower bound of the width, because increasing the width doesn't serve very much of a purpose other than to prevent LTB.

3.4 Nonlinear Constraints

We included the normal constraints that one would have in a truss optimization problem, namely:

1. A stress constraint keeping every member's axial stress less than the tensile strength of the material.

2. A stress constraint keeping the negative of every member’s axial stress less than the tensile strength of the material.
3. An Euler buckling constraint.
4. A displacement constraint keeping the maximum downward displacement of the IsoBeam less than 1.5 inches.

We have two stress constraints for every member, one buckling constraint for every member, and one displacement constraint for the entire IsoBeam. Because there were 1000 members, this resulted in 3001 nonlinear constraints. We scaled all of our nonlinear constraints to be order one.

3.5 Objective Function

Profit and monetary loss is what drives our beautiful market system. For aircraft manufacturers, this almost always translates to wanting the lowest weight aircraft possible to reduce fuel costs. We chose to minimize the volume of material used in our IsoBeam, which is directly proportional to the weight.

4 Results

Figure 5 shows the right half of our optimized IsoBeam with members in tension as red and members in compression as blue. Larger member areas are indicated by thicker line segments. A table in the appendix shows our optimal design variables. Interestingly, thickest members are the longitudinal members in the middle of the beam. We believe that this occurred because it was the most efficient way to stiffen the beam in order to satisfy the deflection constraint. The members on the ends are thinner because they are governed by the tensile stress and buckling constraints. Figure 6 shows a convergence plot for our optimization. The first order optimality unexpectedly spikes just as the objective function is about to converge. Also worth noting is that the objective function was fairly flat for 15 iterations, but then finds a decline. We believe that the optimization must have been in some sort of local valley before it finally found its way down a new descent direction. The table below shows a comparison of the weight of the completed aluminum aircraft floor beam from CEEn 523 and the weight of our optimal IsoBeam. Although we hoped for even better results, a 10% decrease in weight is not a trivial gain in the eyes of aircraft manufacturers.

Beam	Weight [lbs]
Aluminum I-Beam	20.1
Carbon-Epoxy IsoBeam	18.0

Figure 5: Right half of the optimized IsoBeam

Figure 6: Convergence plot for our optimization showing objective function value and first order optimality

5 Conclusions

We conclude that a structural aircraft IsoBeam is around 10% lighter than the standard aluminum beam most commonly used. This result is not the exact absolute optimum, but could be further improved by allowing variation in member areas across the entire length of the beam. Though not a large percentage, this weight reduction could save aircraft industries significant amounts of money over an aircraft's lifetime. One of the largest drawbacks to the incorporation of IsoBeam structures in aircraft is the complex and tedious manufacturing process currently required [5]. As more automated processes are developed, it will become much more advantageous to use the IsoBeam in place of aluminum.

References

- [1] A. B. Strong, D. W. Jensen, The ultimate composite structure, *Composites Fabrication* (2002) 22–27.
- [2] M. E. Rackliffe, D. W. Jensen, W. K. Lucas, Local and global buckling of ultra-lightweight isotruss® structures, *Composites science and technology* 66 (2) (2006) 283–288.
- [3] Isotruss industries.
URL <http://www.isotruss.com/>
- [4] L. R. Francom, D. W. Jensen, Three-dimensional iso-tross structure, uS Patent 5,921,048 (Jul. 13 1999).
- [5] B. A. Asay, Bending behavior of carbon-epoxy isobeam structures, Ph.D. thesis (2015).
- [6] M. Mohagheh, Floor Structure Design Project.

6 Appendix

Design Variable	Optimal Value
Truss Height	10.5
Truss Width	5
Longitudinals 1	0.0821
Inner Diagonals 1	0.0304
Outer Diagonals 1	0.0330
Longitudinals 2	0.0637
Inner Diagonals 2	0.0233
Outer Diagonals 2	0.0242
Longitudinals 3	0.128
Inner Diagonals 3	0.0157
Outer Diagonals 3	0.0149

```
function [ kmems, khats ] = AssembleKmems( n_el, mat_props, CS_props, element_fixities )
%{
Assembles element stiffness matrices given information about the elements
```

Parameters

```
n_el : int
    number of elements in the structure
StructConn: (n_el x 2) matrix
    connectivity matrix for whole structure
    where each row correponds to an element
    and the two elements in that row are the
    nodes that connect the element
Xstruct: (njoint x 3) matrix
    Matrix whose rows corresponds to the joints
    or nodes of the structure and whose three columns
    correspond to the 3 global coordinates of that joint
mat_props: (nmat x 2) matrix
    Matrix whose rows correspond to different materials
    and whose first column = E (Youngs Modulus) and whose
    second columns = G (Shear Modulus)
CS_props: (nCS x 4) matrix
    Matrix whose rows correspond to different cross sections
    and whose columns correspond to A, J, Iy, Iz respectively
element_fixities: (n_el, 4) matrix
    Matrix whose rows correspond to elements and whose columns
    correspond to the fixities of that element Ey1, Ey2, Ez1, Ez2
    where 1 correspond to the end with the first node and 2 corresponds to
    the end with the second node. 1 = fixed, 0 = free to rotate
element_mat: (n_el x 1) vector
```

Vector that contains **which** material is used **for** each different element
element_CS: (n_el x 1) vector

Vector that contains **which cross** section is used **for** each different element

Lengths: (n_el x 1) vector

Vector of element lengths

Rots: (3,3,n_el) matrix

Array of element rotation matrices

Outputs

kmems: (12,12,n_el) Matrix

The collection of the element stiffness matrices

%}

```
kmems = zeros(12,12,n_el);
```

```
khats = zeros(12,12,n_el);
```

```
for ielem = 1:n_el
```

```
    khat = zeros(12,12);
```

```
    E = mat_props(element_mat(ielem),1);
```

```
    G = mat_props(element_mat(ielem),2);
```

```
    Area = CS_props(element_CS(ielem),1);
```

```
    J = CS_props(element_CS(ielem),2);
```

```
    I_y = CS_props(element_CS(ielem),3);
```

```
    I_z = CS_props(element_CS(ielem),4);
```

```
    e_y1 = element_fixities(ielem,1);
```

```
    e_y2 = element_fixities(ielem,2);
```

```
    e_z1 = element_fixities(ielem,3);
```

```
    e_z2 = element_fixities(ielem,4);
```

```
    L = Lengths(ielem);
```

```
    rot = Rots(:, :, ielem);
```

```
    a = E * Area / L;
```

```
    b = G * J / L;
```

```
    c1 = 3 * E * I_y / L / L / L * (e_y1 + e_y2 + 2 * e_y1*e_y2);
```

```
    c2 = 3 * E * I_y / L / L * (e_y1 + e_y1*e_y2);
```

```
    c3 = 3 * E * I_y / L / L * (e_y2 + e_y1*e_y2);
```

```
    c4 = 3 * E * I_y / L * (e_y1 + e_y1*e_y2 / 3);
```

```
    c5 = 3 * E * I_y / L * (e_y2 + e_y1*e_y2 / 3);
```

```
    c6 = 2 * E * I_y * e_y1 * e_y2 / L;
```

```
    d1 = 3 * E * I_z / L / L / L * (e_z1 + e_z2 + 2 * e_z1*e_z2);
```

```
    d2 = 3 * E * I_z / L / L * (e_z1 + e_z1*e_z2);
```

```
    d3 = 3 * E * I_z / L / L * (e_z2 + e_z1*e_z2);
```

```
    d4 = 3 * E * I_z / L * (e_z1 + e_z1*e_z2 / 3);
```

```
    d5 = 3 * E * I_z / L * (e_z2 + e_z1*e_z2 / 3);
```

```
    d6 = 2 * E * I_z * e_z1 * e_z2 / L;
```

```

khat(0+1, 0+1) = a;
khat(1+1, 1+1) = d1;
khat(2+1, 2+1) = c1;
khat(3+1, 3+1) = b;
khat(4+1, 4+1) = c4;
khat(5+1, 5+1) = d4;
khat(6+1, 6+1) = a;
khat(7+1, 7+1) = d1;
khat(8+1, 8+1) = c1;
khat(9+1, 9+1) = b;
khat(10+1, 10+1) = c5;
khat(11+1, 11+1) = d5;
khat(0+1, 6+1) = -1 * a;
khat(6+1, 0+1) = khat(0+1, 6+1);
khat(1+1, 5+1) = d2;
khat(5+1, 1+1) = d2;
khat(1+1, 7+1) = -1 * d1;
khat(7+1, 1+1) = khat(1+1, 7+1);
khat(1+1, 11+1) = d3;
khat(11+1, 1+1) = khat(1+1, 11+1);
khat(2+1, 4+1) = -1 * c2;
khat(4+1, 2+1) = khat(2+1, 4+1);
khat(2+1, 8+1) = -1 * c1;
khat(8+1, 2+1) = khat(2+1, 8+1);
khat(2+1, 10+1) = -1 * c3;
khat(10+1, 2+1) = khat(2+1, 10+1);
khat(3+1, 9+1) = -1 * b;
khat(9+1, 3+1) = khat(3+1, 9+1);
khat(4+1, 8+1) = c2;
khat(8+1, 4+1) = khat(4+1, 8+1);
khat(4+1, 10+1) = c6;
khat(10+1, 4+1) = khat(4+1, 10+1);
khat(5+1, 7+1) = -1 * d2;
khat(7+1, 5+1) = khat(5+1, 7+1);
khat(5+1, 11+1) = d6;
khat(11+1, 5+1) = khat(5+1, 11+1);
khat(7+1, 11+1) = -1 * d3;
khat(11+1, 7+1) = khat(7+1, 11+1);
khat(8+1, 10+1) = c3;
khat(10+1, 8+1) = khat(8+1, 10+1);
khats(:, :, ielem) = khat;

```

```

T = zeros(12,12);
T(1:3,1:3) = rot;

```

```

    T(4:6,4:6) = rot;
    T(7:9,7:9) = rot;
    T(10:12,10:12) = rot;
        khat = T.' * khat * T;
    kmems(:, :, ielem) = khat;
end

end

function [rmem] = SFrameReac(rot, kmem, umem, fmem)
%{
Computes the element reactions after the analysis has found the
displacements

Parameters
-----
rot : 3x3 matrix
      element rotation matrix
kmem: 12x12 matrix
      element stiffness matrix
umem: 12x1 vector
      vector with the nodal displacements and rotations for the element
fmem: 12x1 vector
      element force vector

Outputs
-----
rmem: 12x1 vector
      reaction forces and moments in element
%}

r = kmem * umem - fmem; %%element reactions in global coordinates
T = zeros(12,12);
T(1:3,1:3) = rot;
T(4:6,4:6) = rot;
T(7:9,7:9) = rot;
T(10:12,10:12) = rot;
rmem = T * r; %% this transforms the force vec from global to local coords

end

function [K, Ksup] = AssembleStructureStiffnessMatrix(ndir, n_el, ndof, nsup,
%{
Computes the structure force vector given connectivity, dof numbering and
all the individual fmems.

```

Parameters

`ndir` : int
number of displacement directions per joint

`n_el` : int
number of elements

`ndof`: int
number of structural degrees of freedom

`nsup`: int
number of support displacements specified

`StructConn`: (`n_elements` x 2) matrix
connectivity matrix **for** whole structure
where each row corresponds to an element
and the two elements in that row are the
nodes that connect the element

`dof`: (`njoint` x `ndir`) matrix
matrix of structure dof numbering

`kmems`: (`12` x `12` x `n_elements`) matrix
basically an array of element stiffness
matrices where the third index is the
element index

Outputs

`K` : `ndof` x `ndof` matrix
structure stiffness matrix

%}

`K = zeros(ndof, ndof);` *%%initializing the structure stiffness matrix*

`Ksup = zeros(ndof, nsup);`

`elem_dofs = zeros(1, 12);`

for `ielem = 1:n_el` *%%looping through each element*

`conn = StructConn(ielem, :);`

`knem = kmems(:, :, ielem);`

`counter = 1;`

for `inode = 1:2`

for `idir = 1:ndir`

`elem_dofs(1, counter) = dof(conn(inode), idir);`

`counter = counter + 1;`

end

end

for `irow = 1:12`

for `jcol = 1:12`

if (`elem_dofs(1, irow) > 0` && `elem_dofs(1, jcol) > 0`)

`K(elem_dofs(1, irow), elem_dofs(1, jcol)) = K(elem_dofs(1, irow), elem_dofs(1, jcol));`

```

        elseif (elem_dofs(1,irow) < 0 && elem_dofs(1,jcol) > 0)
            Ksup(elem_dofs(1,jcol),-1*elem_dofs(1,irow)) = Ksup(elem_dofs(1,
        end
    end
end
end
end

```

function [F, usup] = AssembleStructureForceVector(ndir, n_el, ndof, nsup, njointload, jointload, point, StructConn, dof, fmems)

%{
 Assembles the structure force vector from fmems and joint loads

Parameters

ndir : int
 number of displacement directions per joint

n_el : int
 number of elements

ndof: int
 number of structural degrees of freedom

nsup: int
 number of support displacements specified

njointload: int
 number of jointloads (loads and displacements)

jointload: (njointload x 2) matrix
 A matrix whose rows corresponds to jointloads and whose first column is the joint at **which** the **load** acts and the second columns is the direction in **which** the **load** acts

point: (njointload x 1) vector
 A vector that has the magnitudes of the loads

StructConn: (n_elements x 2) matrix
 connectivity matrix **for** whole structure where each row correponds to an element and the two elements in that row are the nodes that connect the element

dof: (njoint x ndir) matrix
 matrix of structure dof numbering

fmems: (12,n_el) Matrix
 Matrix the columns of **which** are element force vectors

Outputs

F : ndof x 1 vector
 structure force vector

```

%}
F = zeros(ndof, 1); %%initializing the structure stiffness matrix
usup = zeros(nsup,1);
elem_dofs = zeros(1,12);
for ielem = 1:n_el %%looping through each element
    conn = StructConn(ielem ,:);
    fmem = fmems(:,ielem);
    counter = 1;
    for inode = 1:2
        for idir = 1:ndir
            elem_dofs(1,counter) = dof(conn(inode),idir);
            counter = counter + 1;
        end
    end
    for irow = 1:12
        if (elem_dofs(irow) > 0)
            F(elem_dofs(irow)) = F(elem_dofs(irow))+fmem(irow);
        end
    end
end
end
if (njointload > 0)
    for ijointload = 1:njointload
        if (dof(jointload(ijointload,1),jointload(ijointload,2)) > 0)
            F(dof(jointload(ijointload,1),jointload(ijointload,2))) =
F(dof(jointload(ijointload,1),jointload(ijointload,2))) + point(ijointload);
        elseif (dof(jointload(ijointload,1),jointload(ijointload,2)) < 0)
            usup(-1*dof(jointload(ijointload,1),jointload(ijointload,2))) = u
        end
    end
end
end
end

```

```

function [ndof, nsup, dof] = StructDOF(njoint, ndir, nsupport, support, njointload);
%}

```

Numbers the **global** DOFs and figures out how many there are and how many support displacements there are

Parameters

njoint : int
 number of joints in the structure
ndir: int
 number of displacement directions per joint
nsupport: int
 number of supports

```

support: (nsupport,2) matrix
    joint and direction of each support
njointload: int
    number of jointloads
jointload: (njointload,2) matrix
    joint and direction of each load

```

Outputs

```

ndof: int
    number of DOFs at the unsupported joints
nsup: int
    number of DOFs at the supported joints
dof :(njoint , ndir) matrix
    matrix of DOF numbering
%}

dof = zeros(njoint , ndir);
for j = 1:njoint
    for d = 1:ndir
        dof(j, d) = 1;
    end
end

for i = 1:nsupport
    j = support(i, 1);
    d = support(i, 2);
    dof(j, d) = 0;
end

    for i=1:njointload
        j = jointload(i, 1);
        d = jointload(i, 2);
        if (dof(j, d) == 0)
            dof(j, d) = -1;
        end
    end
end

ndof = 0;
nsup = 0;

for j=1:njoint
    for d=1:ndir
        if (dof(j, d) == 1)
            ndof = ndof + 1;

```

```

                                dof(j, d) = ndof;
        end
                                if (dof(j, d) == -1)
                                    nsup = nsup + 1;
                                    dof(j, d) = -1 * nsup;
        end
    end
end
end

end

function [ rhats ] = CalculateMemberReactions( umems, Rots, khats, fhats, n_el)
%UNTITLED2 Summary of this function goes here
% Detailed explanation goes here
rhats = zeros(12,n_el);

for ielem=1:n_el
    rot = Rots(:, :, ielem);
    T = zeros(12,12);
    T(1:3,1:3) = rot;
    T(4:6,4:6) = rot;
    T(7:9,7:9) = rot;
    T(10:12,10:12) = rot;
    uhat = T * umems(:, ielem);
    khat = khats(:, :, ielem);
    fhat = fhats(:, ielem);
    rhats(:, ielem) = (khat * uhat) - fhat;
end

end

function [ fmems, fhats ] = AssembleFmems( n_el, element_fixities, Lengths, R)
%{
Assembles element stiffness matrices given information about the elements

Parameters
-----
n_el : int
    number of elements in the structure
element_fixities: (n_el, 4) matrix
    Matrix whose rows correspond to elements and whose columns
    correspond to the fixities of that element Ey1, Ey2, Ez1, Ez2
    where 1 correspond to the end with the first node and 2 corresponds to
    the end with the second node. 1 = fixed, 0 = free to rotate
Lengths: (n_el x 1) vector

```

Vector of element lengths
 Rots: (3,3,n_el) matrix
 Array of element rotation matrices
 load_sets: (n_loads x 8) matrix
 Matrix, each row corresponding to a **load set**, with 8 components
 element_loads: (n_el x 1) vector
 Vector containing **which load set** to put on each member
 Outputs

fmems: (12,n_el) Matrix

Matrix the columns of **which** are element force vectors

`%}`

`fmems = zeros(12,n_el);`

`fhats = zeros(12,n_el);`

`for ielem = 1:n_el`

`fmem = zeros(12,1);`

`fhat = zeros(12,1);`

`wx = load_sets(element_loads(ielem),1);`

`wy = load_sets(element_loads(ielem),2);`

`wz = load_sets(element_loads(ielem),3);`

`wt = load_sets(element_loads(ielem),4);`

`sx = load_sets(element_loads(ielem),5);`

`sy = load_sets(element_loads(ielem),6);`

`sz = load_sets(element_loads(ielem),7);`

`st = load_sets(element_loads(ielem),8);`

`e_y1 = element_fixities(ielem,1);`

`e_y2 = element_fixities(ielem,2);`

`e_z1 = element_fixities(ielem,3);`

`e_z2 = element_fixities(ielem,4);`

`length = Lengths(ielem);`

`rot = Rots(:, :, ielem);`

`a1 = wx * length / 2 + sx * length / 6;`

`a2 = wx * length / 2 + sx * length / 3;`

`b1 = wt * length / 2 + st * length / 6;`

`b2 = wt * length / 2 + st * length / 3;`

`c1 = wz * length / 2 + sz * length / 6 + wz * length / 8 * (e_y1 - e_`

`c2 = wz * length * length / 8 * (e_y1 - e_y1 * e_y2 / 3) + sz * length`

`c3 = wz * length / 2 + sz * length / 3 - wz * length / 8 * (e_y1 - e_`

`c4 = wz * length * length / 8 * (e_y2 - e_y1 * e_y2 / 3) + sz * length`

`d1 = wy * length / 2 + sy * length / 6 + wy * length / 8 * (e_z1 - e_`

`d2 = wy * length * length / 8 * (e_z1 - e_z1 * e_z2 / 3) + sy * length`

`d3 = wy * length / 2 + sy * length / 3 - wy * length / 8 * (e_z1 - e_`

`d4 = wy * length * length / 8 * (e_z2 - e_z1 * e_z2 / 3) + sy * length *`

```

        vec1 = [a1, d1, c1]';
        vec2 = [b1, -1 * c2, d2]';
        vec3 = [a2, d3, c3]';
        vec4 = [b2, c4, -1 * d4]';
    fhat(1:3) = vec1;
    fhat(4:6) = vec2;
    fhat(7:9) = vec3;
    fhat(10:12) = vec4;
    fhats(:,ielem) = fhat;

    vec1 = rot' * vec1;
    vec2 = rot' * vec2;
    vec3 = rot' * vec3;
    vec4 = rot' * vec4;
    fmem(1:3) = vec1;
    fmem(4:6) = vec2;
    fmem(7:9) = vec3;
    fmem(10:12) = vec4;

    fmems(:,ielem) = fmem;

end

end

function [ umems ] = AssembleUmems( StructConn, DOF ,n_el , ndir , U, Usup )
%UNTITLED Summary of this function goes here
% Detailed explanation goes here
umems = zeros(12,n_el);
for ielem = 1:n_el
    counter = 1;
    for ijoint = 1:2
        for idir = 1:6
            joint = StructConn(ielem ,ijoint);
            dof_number = DOF(joint ,idir);
            if (dof_number == 0)
                umems(counter ,ielem) = 0;
            elseif (dof_number > 0)
                umems(counter , ielem) = U(dof_number);
            elseif (dof_number < 0)
                umems(counter ,ielem) = Usup(-1 * dof_number);
            end
            counter = counter + 1;
        end
    end
end

```

end

end

```
function [ Lengths , Rots ] = SFrameLenRot( n_el , StructConn , XStruct , element_o
%{
This function
```

Parameters

n_el : int

number of elements in the structure

StructConn: (n_el x 2) matrix

connectivity matrix **for** whole structure
where each row correponds to an element
and the two elements in that row are the
nodes that connect the element

Xstruct: (njoint x 3) matrix

Matrix whose rows corresponds to the joints
or nodes of the structure and whose three columns
correspond to the 3 **global** coordinates of that joint

element_oriens: (n_el x 3)

Matrix whose rows corresponds to elements and whose columns are vectors
that are in the plane of **what** would be considered the web **if** it were an
I-beam. If the **cross** section is symmetric accross **all axis** then this
doesnt matter

Outputs

Lengths: (n_el , 1) Vector

Lengths of Each individual member

Rots: (3,3,n_el) matrix

Array of element rotation matrices

```
%}
```

```
Rots = zeros(3,3,n_el);
```

```
Lengths = zeros(n_el,1);
```

```
for ielem = 1:n_el
```

```
    node1 = StructConn(ielem,1);
```

```
    node2 = StructConn(ielem,2);
```

```
    orient = element_oriens(ielem,:);
```

```
    orient = orient / norm(orient);
```

```
    rot0 = XStruct(node2,:) - XStruct(node1,:);
```

```
    L = norm(rot0);
```

```
    rot0 = rot0 * (1 / L);
```

```
    rot1 = cross(orient , rot0);
```

```
rot1 = rot1/norm(rot1);
rot2 = cross(rot0,rot1);
rot2 = rot2/norm(rot2);

Lengths(ielem) = L;
Rots(1, :, ielem) = rot0;
Rots(2, :, ielem) = rot1;
Rots(3, :, ielem) = rot2;
end

end
```